

**JOB SATISFACTION OF TEACHERS
ATTACHED TO THE SPECIAL EDUCATION UNITS
IN REGULAR SCHOOL IN SRI LANKA**

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Abstract:

Many studies have been done in developed countries in relation to the importance of job satisfaction of special education teachers. (Salehi, Taghavi, & Yunus, 2015); However, only a limited number of studies have been conducted on special education unit teachers' job satisfaction in Sri Lanka. Therefore, the present study attempts to investigate the job satisfaction of teachers who work under special education unit system in the Northern Province of Sri Lanka. In this study both qualitative and quantitative research methods including in-depth interview protocols and questionnaires were utilized. To collect quantitative data, validated questionnaires were administered to a sample of 213 teachers who teach in special education units established in regular schools of Northern Province in Sri Lanka. After collecting the completed questionnaires, 12 special education unit teachers were selected for an interview. Both quantitative and qualitative data were categorized, coded and analyzed based upon the research objectives and the respective research questions. The results revealed that there is a significant variation in personal information among special education unit teachers, significant positive correlation between variables of teachers' job satisfaction and age, gender, experience, qualification and appointment type. Moreover, teachers have high job satisfaction in their job (average mean value – 3.68 and SD 1.01). However, stakeholder's attitude is main challenge to get satisfaction in the job the teachers. Based on the findings of the study, it can recommended be that stakeholders should be aware regarding special education and they need to develop positive attitude on special education. Therefore, Ministry of Education and Department of Education of Northern Province have to raise necessary actions to make awareness among parents, community members, regular classroom teachers, principals and administrative staffs, a policy on education of disabled students should also be developed at provincial level.

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1. Introduction

The concept of job satisfaction has been extensively studied across the world and more than twelve thousand studies were published in the Nineties of the Twentieth century, which bears testimony to the importance of this issue (Gazzawi, 2008). Another study indicated, job satisfaction is at the top of the priority list of any institution which aims to retain exceptional and distinguished competent staff (Abushaira, 2012). Especially, in the field of special education, in recent years, more and more people around the world are in need of acquiring a higher level of competence in teaching children with special needs as it is becoming more popular in the world. As such, job satisfaction takes a central place among special education teachers. Recently, the World Report on Disability-WHO estimated the prevalence of disability to be higher than previously estimated, with a suggestion of up to 15% of the population said to experience disabilities in resource-limited countries including Sri Lanka (Ekanayake, et. al, 2016). Moreover, The Foundation for the Rehabilitation of the Disabled estimates that there are 40,000 people disabled by the war living in Northern Sri Lanka due to 30 years of war (Perera, 2015). Therefore, initiatives should be taken to improve special education especially in Northern Sri Lanka. Special education teachers play a vital role in implementation of special education; however, the attrition, or “burn-out,” rate for special education teachers is extremely high compared to most other professions due to lack of factors such as appreciation, parental support, and public support, as well as heavy workload on paperwork. The need to collaboration with regular classroom teachers, data collection on evidence of growth of students and the diversity of student’s needs (Ferry, 2012).

Moreover, the works done by the special education teacher can be emotionally demanding and physically draining. Many special education teachers are under considerable stress due to heavy workloads and administrative tasks. They must produce a substantial amount of paperwork documenting each student's progress and work under the threat of litigation against the school or district by parents if correct procedures are not followed or if the parents feel that their child is not receiving an adequate education (Sokanu.org, 2017). According to the above literature, many factors influence the job satisfaction of special education teachers. Thus, improving special education teachers’ job satisfaction can act as one crucial step in improving the special education system in regular schools. Moreover, so far, no studies have been conducted on job satisfaction of special education unit teachers with special reference to northern Sri Lanka. Therefore, the present study tries to investigate the job satisfaction of teachers attached to the special education unit system in the Northern Province of Sri Lanka.

Special education has been practiced in three forms in the Sri Lankan education system, residential special schools, special education unit system, and enrolling

students with special educational needs straight away to normal classrooms. This research study focuses on the special education unit system form of special education system in Northern Sri Lanka.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Job Satisfaction

According to Redmond (2016), job satisfaction is one of the most extensively researched subjects in Industrial/Organizational Psychology (Judge & Church, 2000). Moreover, several works on motivation theories have corroborated the important role of job satisfaction. Work satisfaction theories, such as Maslow's (1943) Hierarchy of Needs, Herzberg's (1968) Two-Factor (Motivator-Hygiene) Theory, Adam's (1965) Equity Theory, Porter and Lawler's (1968) modified version of Vroom's (1964) VIE Model, Locke's (1969) Discrepancy Theory, Hackman and Oldham's (1976) Job Characteristics Model, Locke's (1976) Range of Affect Theory, Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory, and Landy's (1978) Opponent Process Theory, have tried to conceptualize job satisfaction and its influence.

Such expansive research has recently resulted in job satisfaction being linked to productivity, motivation, absenteeism/tardiness, accidents, mental/physical health, and general life satisfaction. Actually, a common theory within the research literature has been that, to an extent, the emotional state of an individual is affected by interactions within their work environment (Redmond, 2016). Moreover, some aspects related to job satisfaction as highlighted in research title include payment for the job, work responsibilities, task variety, opportunities for promotion, the work itself, and coworkers. In addition to that, other key factors include general well-being, stress at work, control at work, the home-work interface, and working conditions. Some researchers divide the variables as environmental and individual factors (Jeffrey & Vincent, 2013); these factors are the job satisfaction of teachers directly or indirectly.

However, Hackman & Oldham (1980) and Smith, Kendall, & Hulin (1969) listed out a range variable in relation to job satisfaction such as autonomy in job, task significance, supervision in job, school rules and job conditions, knowledge and skills in job, feedback in job, parents' support, improvement opportunities in job, school community relationship in job, payment for job, various skills for job, other teachers' relationship in job, over workload and job stress. These variables can be considered as factors that affect job satisfaction of special education unit teachers.

2.1.1 Job satisfaction of special education teachers

Recently, several research studies have investigated job satisfaction of special education teachers. Strydom et al (2012) indicate that teachers experienced an average level of job satisfaction. In addition to this finding, differences were also found in the levels of job satisfaction among different races, but not between genders. Moreover, another study found that the level of job satisfaction helps to improve teachers' work efficacy, and also

highlighted the necessity of providing an appropriate work atmosphere to encourage the teachers who work with the multi-disabled students (Abushaira, 2012). Moreover, the study recommended that, it would be a best if the teachers' pay is proportionally equal, and every teacher will be employed by the Ministry of Education. Teachers' professional development opportunity has a significant relationship with the level of teachers' performance and satisfaction (Shourbagi & Bakkar, 2015). However, teachers' job satisfaction is influenced by education planners. Ministry of Education takes action to create more awareness on special needs education to the society (Wangari, & Orodho, 2014) to develop the job satisfaction among special education unit teachers. The above-mentioned findings show factors that affect job satisfaction of special education teachers.

2.1.2 Job satisfaction of teachers in Sri Lanka

There are a number of studies conducted on job satisfaction of teachers in Northern Sri Lanka. These research studies present important recommendations in relation to the area of study. For instance Mangaleswarasarma (2017) recommends that teachers in Northern Sri Lanka should be provided with relevant training and professional development opportunities, an increase of salary and they should be given respect and recognition to motivate them and to increase their job satisfaction (Mangaleswarasharma, 2017). Moreover, when the drafts on policies in terms of the pay structure and administration of the school teachers especially in the northern part of Sri Lanka are being made, governmental bodies like Ministry of Education should consider the differences in the level of pay satisfaction among personal characteristics (Achchuthan, et. al., 2014). Some of the findings in the research literature highlighted the relationship between job satisfaction and efficiency of work, and policies or practices that can be used to enhance the employee job satisfaction and organizational performance (Kanojan & Sivalogathan, 2017). In addition, Fernando (2017) states that teachers' educational qualifications significantly impact on their intrinsic job satisfaction. The trends of negative effects of job satisfaction are visible displayed in public sector school teachers of Sri Lanka (Fernando, 2015). Autocratic leadership has a negative impact on teachers' job satisfaction. On the contrary, democratic leadership has a positive impact on job satisfaction (Thuraisingam, & Nadarasa, 2014). No studies on job satisfaction of special education unit or special education teachers in Northern Sri Lanka are available. Therefore, the researcher reviewed the studies in relation to general classroom teachers' job satisfaction and the literature reviewed shows that there is a need to explore the job satisfaction of special education teachers attached to the units in the Northern Province schools in Sri Lanka.

3. Objectives

- To identify the job satisfaction level of special education unit teachers in Northern Sri Lanka.

- To examine the relationship between job satisfaction and personal factors of special education unit teachers in Northern Sri Lanka.
- To find out the factors that affect job satisfaction of special education unit teaches in Northern Sri Lanka.
- To make suggestions to improve the job satisfaction of special education unit teaches in Northern Sri Lanka.

4. Methodology

This study followed the survey design and mixed (qualitative and quantitative) method approach.

4.1 Participants

Purposive sampling method was used for this study. Participants of the study were teachers who were employed under the special education unit system in regular schools in the Northern Provincial the time of the study. Sample considered of both female and male teachers (54 female, 159 male) and both permanent and volunteer teachers (189 permanent and 24 volunteer) who different in terms of years of experience as special education teacher (from a month to 20 years).

4.2 Data Collection Instruments

Both questionnaires and interview schedules were utilized to collect the required data. A questionnaire was used to collect both quantitative data. In addition, qualitative data and interviews were conducted to obtain qualitative data that could help explore details collected from the quantitative survey in-depth.

4.3 Teachers' Questionnaire

The purpose of this questionnaire was to collect demographic data about special education unit teachers (gender, age, experience, educational qualifications etc.) and their job satisfaction (aspects such as autonomy, work itself, working conditions, task significance, supervision, stress, social relationships, co-workers' relations, feedback, workload, skill variety, pay, skill identity and promotion opportunities). The teacher's questionnaire was developed by the researcher and was piloted on 25 special education unit teachers; subsequently Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated.

Table 1: The Results of the Reliability Test Variables

Variable	Number of Items	Means	Cronbach's Alpha
Job satisfaction	14	3.675	0.863

Shown in Table 1, the Cronbach's alpha value for the variable exceeded the minimum required value of 0.7 (Salehi, Taghavi, & Yunus, 2015) and hence, the scale of variable is highly reliable.

4.4 Interview

The second tool for gathering information was the interview protocol. The interviews the qualitative part in this study, was used to gain in-depth information in addition to the data collected through the questionnaire. 12 special education unit teachers were selected for an interview. While the questionnaire gave a general understanding to on nature of teachers' job satisfaction, the interviews provided more detailed information. The purpose of the interview questions was to probe more deeply the perceptions of Northern Province special education unit teachers on their overall job satisfaction.

4.5 Procedure

Two hundred and forty-five (245) questionnaires were distributed among the special education unit teachers teaching in the Northern provincial schools in Sri Lanka. After 35 days, two hundred and twenty-one (221) questionnaires were collected; however, 08 questionnaires were discarded from the analysis process due to major data-missing and only two hundred and thirteen (213) questionnaires were considered for data entry and analysis. Twelve special education unit teachers from twelve educational zones of Northern Province who had already participated in the survey were invited for the interview; however, only ten were interviewed. All the interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim so that the risk of missing the interviewees' comments was reduced. Finally, the transcribed interviews were organized, coded and analyzed.

5. Results

The data was tabulated and analyzed using statistical package SPSS, version 16.0. The analysis of the qualitative part of the study, which considered of open ended questions included in questionnaires and involved personal interviews with teachers, started after collecting the qualitative data because the collected information was fresh in the researcher's mind.

5.1 Data Analysis (Quantitative Part - 1)

The first part consisted of six items on teachers' personal characteristics related to demographic information including gender, age, academic qualifications, professional qualifications, types of appointment, years of teaching experience etc. As shown in Table 2, the majority of the respondents were female constituting 74.6% of the samples.

Table 2: Respondents' Gender Profiles

Gender	Frequency	Valid percent
Female	159	74.6
Male	54	25.4
Total	213	100

Figure 1 illustrates the age profiles of the participants. As shown, 53.5% of participants in age range of 26-35 it's the majority in age range.

Figure 1: Respondents' Age Profiles

According to Table 3, majority (55.4%) of the participants had 1-3 years of work experience as a special education unit teacher.

Table 3: Respondents' Experiences

Experiences in years	Frequency	Percent
1-3	118	55.4
4-6	50	23.5
7-9	27	12.7
10-12	18	8.5
Total	213	100.0

Figure 2 illustrates the participants' professional qualification level. As shown, most (92%) of the respondents had a National Diploma in Teaching (special education). Mean value is 2.85 and SD is 0.783.

Figure 2: Respondents' Professional Qualification

Figure 3 also illustrates the participants' types of appointment. As shown, most (89%) of the respondents have been appointed permanently in special education units, and 11% of participants have been appointed as volunteers in special education units.

Figure 3: Respondents' Appointment Types

5.2 Data Analysis (Quantitative Part - 2)

The second part consisted of 14 variables in relation to the job satisfaction such as autonomy in job, task significance in job, supervision in job, school rules and conditions of job, knowledge and skills in job, workload in job, feedback in job, stress in job, improvement opportunities in job, school community relationship in job, parents' support in job, salary for job, skills to meet diversity student in job and other teachers' relationship in job. Likert scale was used to investigate the level of satisfactions on each variable in relation to the job satisfaction of teachers who are employed under special education unit system.

Table 4 illustrates the special education unit teachers' satisfaction level on each variable by using the mean value and SD of participants' responses. The results show that special education unit teachers have satisfaction on autonomy in job, task significance in job, supervision in job, school rules and conditions of job, knowledge and skills in job, and feedback in job. Comparably, the above-mentioned variables have a positive average mean value (3,86) and low level of SD ($SD < 1$). It shows that teachers in the special education units have strong satisfaction on the above-mentioned aspects.

Moreover, special education unit teachers have satisfaction on the following aspects; improvement opportunities in job, school community relationship in job, parents' support in job, salary for job, skills to meet diverse needs of student in job, stress in job, and other teachers' relationship in job with higher average mean value (3,78). However, SD is in higher level ($SD > 1$). Therefore, it may comparably weak than above mentioned variables. However, variable of workload in job was responded negatively by the respondents, 2.62 mean value and 0.987 SD. It's seems quite strengthen of their response.

In overall view, participants have satisfaction in various levels of fourteen variables in relation to the job satisfaction. However, participants do not have satisfaction variables of over workload.

Finally, job satisfaction of special education unit teachers is good according to average mean value 3.78 and SD 1.01.

Table 4: Mean value and SD of Responds of Participants

Variables in relation to the job satisfaction	Mean value	SD
Satisfaction regarding autonomy in Job	3.84	.974
Satisfaction regarding task significance in job	4.64	.736
Satisfaction regarding supervision in job	3.93	.990
Satisfaction regarding school rules and conditions of job	3.68	.853
Satisfaction regarding knowledge and skills in job	3.58	.947
Satisfaction regarding feedback in job	3.49	.989
Satisfaction regarding parent's supports in job	4.15	1.184
Satisfaction regarding improvement opportunities in job	3.69	1.123
Satisfaction regarding school community relationship in job	3.45	1.001
Satisfaction regarding salary for job	3.88	1.007
Satisfaction regarding skills to meet diverse needs of students in job	3.76	1.080
Satisfaction regarding other teachers' relationship in job	3.72	1.029
Satisfaction regarding workload in job	2.62	.987
Satisfaction regarding stress in job	3.05	1.229
Average	3.68	1.009

Independent Samples t-Test method was utilized in order to find significant relationship of Gender and Appointment type with variables of job satisfaction in order to identify two groups of participants in each group. The confidence level was 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) for this study. According to the following table all the p – values for conservation concept are greater than 0.05 ($p > \alpha$). Therefore, there is evidence to indicate that the fourteen variables tested have an effect upon performance in conservation tasks. Following Table 5 implies that, parent's support, autonomy in job, task significance in job, supervision in job, school rules and conditions of job, improvement opportunities in job, school community relationship in job, salary for job, skills to meet diversity of students in job, workload in job and other teachers' relationship in job have an effect on the relationship with Gender variation among special education unit teachers in Northern province.

Moreover, parent's support, task significance in job, school rules and conditions of job, stress in job, satisfaction regarding skills to meet diversity of students in job, and feedback in job have an effect on the relationship with Appointment type variation among special education unit teachers in the Northern province.

Table 5: p-Value of the Independent Sample t - Test

SN	Variables	P-value of T-test	
		Gender	Appointment type
1	Parent's supports	.002	.001
2	Autonomy in job	.000	.072
3	Task significance in job	.000	.000
4	Supervision in job	.000	.938
5	School rules and conditions in job	.001	.006
6	Stress in job	.874	.005
7	Improvement opportunities in job	.000	.000
8	Knowledge and skills in job	.172	.094
9	Schools community relationship in job	.000	.054
10	Salary for job	.000	.381
11	Satisfaction regarding skills to meet diverse needs of students in job	.005	.010
12	Workload in job	.000	.522
13	Other teachers' relationship in job	.000	.556
14	Feedback in job	.102	.008

The Kruskal – Wallis Test was utilized to investigate the effect on the relationship of Age, Experiences, and Professional qualifications with variable in relation to job satisfaction, in order to analysis the responses of more than two group of respondents, and non-normality data. According to the Kruskal – Wallis Test, the accepted significant p-value is less than 0.05. The confidence level was 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) for this study. According to the following table-6 numbers of the p – values for conservation concept are below 0.05 ($p > \alpha$). Therefore, there is evidence to indicate that the fourteen variables tested have an effect upon performance in conservation tasks.

Following Table 6 implies that, parent's support in job, autonomy in job, task significance in job, supervision in job, stress in job, improvement opportunities in job, school community relationship in job, salary for job, skills to meet diversity of students in job, workload in job, other teachers' relationship in job, and feedback in job have an effect on the relationship with Age variation among special education unit teachers in Northern province.

Moreover, parent's support, task significance in job, improvement opportunities in job, skills to meet diversity of students in job, workload in job and feedback in job have effect on relationship with Experience variation among special education unit teachers in Northern province.

And also, autonomy in job, task significance in job, supervision in job, school rules and conditions in job, stress in job, improvement opportunities in job, school community relationship in job, salary for job, skills to meet diversity of students in job, other teachers' relationship in job, and feedback in job have an effect on the relationship with experience variation among special education unit teachers in Northern province.

Table 6: p-Value of the Kruskal – Wallis Test

SN	Variables	p-Value of the Kruskal – Wallis Test		
		Age	Experiences	Professional qualification
1	Parent's support in job	.000	.000	.128
2	Autonomy in job	.001	.555	.000
3	Task significance in job	.006	.039	.002
4	Supervision in job	.032	.267	.002
5	School rules and conditions	.148	.383	.011
6	Stress in job	.000	.980	.037
7	Improvement opportunities in job	.002	.000	.037
8	Knowledge and skills in job	.249	.651	.067
9	Community relationship in job	.000	.659	.001
10	Payment for job	.000	.069	.001
11	Skills to meet diverse needs of students in job	.000	.001	.017
12	Workload in job	.000	.034	.078
13	Other teachers' relationship in job	.002	.012	.001
14	Feedback in job	.000	.000	.049

When analyzing in depth, the relationship of variables, can be discussed in two ways. On the one hand, task significance in job, improvement opportunities in job, and skills to meet diversity of students in job variables have an effective relationship with gender, age, experience, professional qualification, and appointment type variables, On the other hand, variable Age has effective relationship with twelve variables out of fourteen variables in relation to the job satisfaction. Moreover, knowledge and skills in job does not have a relationship with any variable in relation to the personal information, however experience of teachers have an effective relationship with only six variables regarding to job satisfaction in relation to the special education unit teachers in Northern province.

5.3 Interview results (Qualitative Part)

This part reported the results obtained from the interviews and open-ended questions of the questionnaire given to teachers who are teaching in the special education unit in the Northern Province. Participants agreed and supported to answer to interview questions and open-ended questionnaire questions.

Most of the teachers responded that, they loved and were satisfied with this job, and they provided their perception on the job such as, it's a service, children with special needs are blessed by god thus it's a good job, gaining actual satisfaction by teaching in the special education unit, it's support for improving children with special educational needs, it's a significant task for this community, happiness in this job, it's seems as social service, it's a special task, and it's give spiritual satisfaction. However, some participants were dissatisfied with the job because it is a difficult task, it is not a recognized job in society, lack of respect in the community, the view that it's an alternative job till a better job can be found, and negative attitudes of community. The above mentioned factors affected on teachers' attitude regarding the job.

Teachers have challenges in relation to their job; the challenges can be categorized according to criteria such as resources, knowledge and skills, awareness, personal challenges, practical challenges etc.

Resources: (physical resources) no separated class/building for special education unit, modified chairs and tables, toilet, playground, assistive technology, inappropriate school environment for children with special needs, inappropriate resources distribution, inappropriate curriculum and teaching methods, and teaching learning instruments, (human resources) inadequate of support of stakeholders such as, parents, community, normal classroom teacher, principals, administrators, and other facilitators. Knowledge and skills: lack of knowledge and skills to meet diverse needs of children in special education unit, developing IEP, lack of training for teachers, lack of opportunities for improving teachers' knowledge and skills, lack of classroom management skills, and lack of in-service training.

Awareness: it's considered as a despicable job by normal classroom teachers, lack of awareness among stakeholders such as parents, community, normal classroom teacher, principals, administrators, and other facilitators, negative attitude of parents with normal children, and no priorities to undertake this special education unit system in schools.

Personal challenges: heavy workload, mentally stress, it's effect on personal life for an instance, 'one marriage proposal was cancelled because of my job', lack of self-esteem and self-reliance.

Practical challenges: lack of knowledge and skills higher level administrative, lack of administrative skills of principals, interference of normal classroom teachers, lack of knowledge regarding curriculum, socialization of children with special needs, and inadequate of students' attendance.

Teachers recommended some suggestions to overcome above mentioned challenges this includes, conducting awareness programmes to each stakeholder, in-service programmes to teacher who teach in special education unit and normal classroom, upgrade to international level all programmes in-relation to special needs education, increase the contribution of stakeholders, conduct evaluation in relation to improvement of special education unit system, developing the special curriculum in school/provincial level, opportunity for vocational trainings children with special needs and developing policy on education of children with special needs.

6. Discussion

According to the analysed personal information, majority of special needs teachers are female, age range is 26-35, have less than 3 years of experiences in their job, national diploma in teacher education (special education) and permanent appointment in their job. When considering analyzed data in-relation to variable of job satisfaction, majority of participant have satisfaction regarding thirteen variables in-relation to their job (mean value range is 3.05 – 4.64). Hence, it's seems that teachers are satisfied with their

job. However, majority of participant have dissatisfaction regarding one variable (workload in job).

Strydom et al, (2012) indicated in their research finding, differences were also found in the levels of job satisfaction between different races, but not between genders. However, when considering the effect on the relationship between gender information and variables regarding job satisfaction, it has an effect on the relationship with some variables in relation to job satisfaction. It's seems against to above mentioned assumption. Moreover, professional qualification, age range and appointment type have an effect on the relationship with variables in relation to job satisfaction. However, experiences of participants have less relationship with variables in relation to job satisfaction.

Abushaira (2012) stated that, necessity of providing an appropriate work atmosphere to encourage the teachers who work with disabled students. However, teachers are disappointed with supports of parents of children with special needs, co-teachers, community, principals, and administrative staff in special education. Shourbagi & Bakkar (2015), Governments would do well to enhance the status of the teaching profession in general and special education. However, the government is not effective with work on enhancing special education unit teachers in the Northern Province. For instance; the teachers are keen to develop their professions but are identified by the lack of programmes to follow in the Northern Province after completing diploma in College of Education.

It is important that school principals become aware of teachers' feelings regarding their competence, job characteristics because it seems to have a significant impact on teachers; level of performance, and consequently on teachers' level of satisfaction Shourbagi & Bakkar (2015). Principals' inadequate support and lack of distribution of resources, inadequate engagement, and assigning unnecessary tasks for special education unit teachers makes getting satisfaction in job more challenging. This practical situation is against the above-mentioned assumption. According to Wangari & Orodho (2014) lack of appropriate training and experience in special education setting, heavy workload due to rapidly growing student population, lack of administrative support and appraisal, and low remuneration as well as poor terms of service, amongst others are influenced in job satisfaction. Participant teachers also have faced same challenges in relation to job satisfaction as special education unit teacher.

7. Conclusion and Implications

A number of researchers have already investigated teachers' job satisfaction and its relationship with different elements. (Bernaus & Wilson, 2008; Caprara, 2006; Corina & Valerica, 2012) However, no study has been conducted in relation to job satisfaction of special education unit teachers in Northern Province, Sri Lanka. In order to gain a better understanding of the nature of job satisfaction of special education unit teachers,

research questions were formed, and data was collected and appropriate research methods were utilized to collect and analyze the data to achieve the goal of the study.

The quantitative findings of the study clearly indicated that there is empirically job satisfaction among special education unit teachers in relation to their job; average mean value is 3.68 and SD is 1.01 it's as seems strong satisfaction. However, special education unit teachers have dissatisfaction over workload in their job (mean value 3.38), as shown, majority of participants satisfied with regard their job as special education unit teacher. Female and younger teachers are interested to work in special education unit system as a permanent teacher with fewer experiences in special education field, and most of the teachers have National Diploma in Education as professional qualification. And majority of teachers have a permanent job. Above mentioned factors in relation to special education unit teacher have significant relationship with variables regarding job satisfaction in various degrees. Age variation has the highest effect on the relationship with variables of job satisfaction of special education unit teachers. However, experience of teachers has less relationship with aspects of job satisfaction of special education unit teachers. Moreover, task significance has influenced in all personal factors.

Challenges faced by special education unit teachers in relation to resources, knowledge and skills, awareness of stakeholders, personal factors, practical challenges etc. affect the job satisfaction of teachers even though they desire the job. Moreover, special education unit teachers desire to overcome the challenges to gain full satisfaction in their job by conducting various programme in the Northern Province. Therefore, the, Ministry of Education and Department of Education of the Northern province have to take necessary action to increase awareness among parents, community members, normal classroom teachers, principals and administrative staffs and have to develop a policy on education of disability students in provincial level.

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